

Thresholds for Fufu Sensory Properties

Umuahia, Nigeria, 10/31/2024

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTB Breeding project, Quality-component (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods project.

To be cited as:

Ugo CHIJIJOKE, Justice OKORONKWO, Ugochi Jane IRO, Precious UDOKA, Sonia OSODEKE, Oluchi ACHONWA, Emmanuel ANIEDO, Simon Peter ABAH, Ogechi UMEZURUMBA, Juliet CHIKERE, Ijeoma OBASI, Tessy MADU, Benjamin OKOYE, Mercy EJECHI, Solomon NWAFOR, Nnaemeka ONYEMAUWA, Miriam OFOEZE, Blessing UKEJE, Samuel ONWUKA, Chinwe ELUAGU (2024). *Thresholds for Fufu Sensory Properties*. Umudike, Nigeria: RTB Breeding, Scientific report, 18 p.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118314>

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTB Breeding project, through a sub-grant from the International Potato Center (CIP) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-041105 between CIP and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF).

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ABSTRACT

Fufu, a staple food in West Africa, is highly valued for its texture, flavor, and color—attributes that significantly influence consumer acceptability. This study aimed to determine the threshold levels of key fufu sensory attributes using a combination of Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA), instrumental texture and color measurements, and consumer preference testing. A comprehensive evaluation was conducted to establish the minimum acceptable (50%) and optimal (70%) thresholds for critical textural and color traits. Instrumental texture analysis revealed that the hardness of fufu dough had an optimal threshold of 960N, with an acceptable range extending to 1180N (precision accuracy: 87.64%). Adhesiveness, a key determinant of stickiness, had an optimal threshold of -400N, with an acceptable maximum of -300N (precision accuracy: 76.11%). Springiness, which contributes to the elasticity of the dough, exhibited an optimal range of 0.41–0.60 (precision accuracy: 80.21%). Cohesiveness, essential for the internal bonding strength of fufu, had an optimal range of 0.36–0.51 (precision accuracy: 88.35%). Instrumental color analysis, based on CIELAB values, established an optimal L* (lightness) value of 58, indicating consumer preference for a moderately bright fufu color, with an acceptable threshold value at 61 (precision accuracy: 84.20%). The a* (green-red spectrum) had an optimal range of -6.08 and an acceptable threshold value at -4.84, while the optimal b*_colour (yellow-blue spectrum) value was 11.48, ensuring an appealing yellowish hue for consumer satisfaction with the acceptable b*_colour value of 25. The QDA and consumer testing further validated these thresholds, highlighting the importance of moldability, smoothness, and stickiness in shaping consumer preferences. The acceptable moldability threshold value was established at 4.5–6.0, while the optimal value was established at 7.55 on the 11-point scale (precision accuracy: 0.805). Smoothness was optimized between 3.20 and 4.6 (precision accuracy: 0.8297). Stickiness was found to be most acceptable at 6.95–7.58 (precision accuracy: 0.891), reflecting a balanced consistency preferred by consumers. These findings provide critical benchmarks for cassava breeding programs, ensuring the selection of genotypes that meet consumer expectations for fufu quality. By integrating instrumental, sensory, and consumer data, this study offers a robust framework for optimizing fufu texture and color attributes, contributing to improved breeding strategies and enhanced consumer satisfaction.

Keywords: Fufu, QDA, instrumental texture, colour measurements, consumer test, threshold

1 OVERVIEW

Fufu, a staple food in West Africa made primarily from cassava, is prized for its distinct texture, flavour, and colour—attributes that are key to consumer acceptability. Previous studies (Teeken et al., 2022; Olaosebikan et al., 2022; Teeken et al., 2021; Ndjouenkeu et al., 2021; Bello et al., 2020) have shown that both processors and consumers prioritize texture and colour when evaluating fufu. Assessing fufu's quality involves a range of methodologies, each offering insights into its sensory and physical characteristics. Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA), conducted with trained panels, provides a detailed sensory profile anchored on capturing variations in the intensity of visual sensory properties of food such as smoothness, stretchability, colour, stickiness and moldability. Alongside this, instrumental methods such as texture analysis (measured with the TA.XT Plus Texture Analyzer) and colour measurement (using the Minolta CR-400 chromameter) objectively assess textural attributes, including hardness, adhesiveness, and cohesiveness, and colour parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* values) in the CIELAB space; where L^* represents lightness; a^* close to zero represents minimal green-red shift and low blue- and b^* equal to yellow. Consumer testing complements these methods by gauging overall acceptability and the JUST-ABOUT-RIGHT (JAR) perception of each trait by the end-user. This study explores the relationship between QDA, instrumental texture and colour measurements, and consumer preferences in order to determine the threshold of key fufu sensory attributes important to consumers..

1.1 Procedure: Sample Preparation

Fresh cassava roots from seven varieties (BABA70, GOVERNOR, NWAOCHA, TMEB419, TMS980505 and TMS011412) were sourced from the genetic gain field at the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria. The preparation of fufu followed the method as described by Chijioke *et al.* (2021). The cooking method involved continuous stirring of the reconstituted fufu paste under steady heat for approximately 5 minutes, as specified in the RTBfoods harmonized standard operating procedure (SOP: <https://doi.org/10.18167/DVN1/SZKUF2>). Also, the RTBfoods harmonized SOP for color measurement was adopted to determine the color profile of the cassava fufu dough samples using a Minolta CR-400 Chromameter.

1.1.1 Texture Analyzer

The Textural Profile Analysis (TPA) of fufu was conducted using a Stable Microsystems TA.XT plus texture analyzer, fitted with a standard cylindrical compression plate of 100 mm diameter. Prior to testing, the texture analyzer was powered on, and the PC was properly connected for data acquisition. TPA test parameters were selected from the instrument's library, and a project folder was created to store the analysis results. Calibration of the probe height and applied force was performed according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Fufu samples with uniform dimensions of 4.0 cm in height and 4.7 cm in diameter were positioned centrally on the instrument's platform, and the sample temperature was equilibrated to 45°C. The

analysis was initiated via the instrument software, and double compression tests were executed automatically, applying a 10g trigger force with a 10-second interval between compressions.

Figure 1 : Texture Analyzer

1.1.2 Chromameter Reading

The colour of cassava fufu dough was measured using a Chromameter Minolta CR-400 (Konica Minolta, Japan), with results reported according to the CIELAB colour system. The instrument was calibrated using a standard white reference ($L^* = 93.30$, $a^* = 0.32$, $b^* = 0.33$). To ensure consistency, the surface of each fufu sample was manually levelled prior to measurement. The measuring head was positioned at two different points on each sample, and measurements were performed in triplicate. The colour parameters were expressed as L^* (lightness, ranging from 0 [black] to 100 [white]), a^* (positive values indicate redness, negative values indicate greenness), and b^* (positive values indicate yellowness, negative values indicate blueness).

Figure 2 : Chromameter for color detection

1.1.3 QDA (Sensory Evaluation)

A sensory evaluation was conducted with 12 trained panellists. Each panellist received a 20 g portion of fufu, served at 45°C on white plastic disposable plates. To assess the homogeneity and repeatability of panel performance, each fufu variety was presented twice: five samples were evaluated during a morning session, with duplicate samples assessed in the afternoon session. Panellists evaluated the samples based on

colour (a^* , b^* and L) and key sensory attributes, such as hardness, adhesiveness, springiness, stickiness, smoothness, mouldability and cohesiveness, using a scale of 0-10 where a lower value indicates lesser intensity while higher value tending towards 10 implies an increased intensity.

Figure 3: Sensory Evaluation

1.1.4 Consumer Testing

A consumer acceptability study was conducted with 124 participants on the seven samples following the RTBfoods (Roots, Tubers, and Bananas) harmonized Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for sensory characterization (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00637>). This standardized methodology ensures consistent sensory attribute evaluation across different studies, enabling reliable comparisons.

The study was carried out in Umuahia South L.G.A, Abia State, Nigeria, a region known for its high fufu consumption, making it an ideal location for assessing local consumer preferences. Participants were selected based on a balanced demographic profile, comprising 57 males and 67 females, with ages ranging from 18 to 65 years. The majority fell within the 25–45 age group, ensuring a diverse representation of young adults and middle-aged individuals.

Each participant received a structured questionnaire to evaluate the sensory attributes of fufu on the hardness, stickiness, smoothness, mouldability and colour. Ratings were provided using a Just-About-Right (JAR) scale, which helps assess whether each attribute is perceived as too low, too high, or just right according to consumer preferences. This approach allows for the identification of optimal levels for key sensory characteristics, ensuring that the product meets consumer expectations.

1.1.5 Threshold Levels Determination

Threshold levels were determined based on consumer preference and descriptive measurements (QDA or instrumental data). For each sensory attribute, an acceptability threshold was determined to satisfy 50% of

consumers, and an optimal threshold was determined to satisfy 70% of consumers. Results obtained were analyzed to ascertain threshold for the sensory attributes of fufu for cassava breeding pipelines.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 THRESHOLD OF JAR AGAINST TEXTURE (INSTRUMENT)

2.1.1 Threshold of Hardness by Instrument

Figure 4 shows that for fufu hardness to satisfy more than 50% of consumers, it must be below 960N, while a threshold of 1180N is required to satisfy over 70% of consumers. This indicates a general preference for softer fufu paste. The coefficient of determination (87.64%) demonstrates a strong model fit to the data. Variations in hardness among genotypes may be attributed to differences in starch composition and gelatinization properties during fufu preparation, underscoring the importance of selecting cassava varieties with optimal textural characteristics to enhance consumer satisfaction.

Figure 4: Threshold of Hardness by Instrument and Consumer Acceptability data

2.1.2 Threshold of Adhesiveness

The results in figure 5 show that for more than 50% of consumers to be satisfied with the adhesiveness of the fufu, it has to be less than -300N. For over 70% of consumers to be satisfied, it needs to be below -400N. This suggests that consumers generally prefer a less sticky fufu paste. The coefficient of determination of 80.17% indicates a good fit of the model to our data. The variability in this trait may be influenced by the water absorption capacity and amylose content of different cassava genotypes, highlighting the importance of selecting varieties with ideal textural properties to enhance consumer satisfaction.

Figure 5: Threshold of Adhesiveness

2.1.3 Threshold of Springiness

Springiness reflects the ability of fufu dough to regain its shape after compression, playing a crucial role in its texture and mouthfeel. The study in Figure 6 determined an optimal threshold range of 0.41–0.60, indicating the preferred level for consumer satisfaction. The precision accuracy of 80.21% suggests that this trait can be measured with reasonable consistency. Springiness is influenced by protein content and the degree of starch gelatinization during processing. Maintaining springiness within the optimal range ensures a soft yet resilient texture, enhancing the overall eating experience. Excessive springiness may make the fufu too elastic, while lower values may result in a mushy texture, reducing consumer preference.

Figure 6: Threshold of Springiness

2.1.4 Threshold of Cohesiveness

Cohesiveness, which represents the internal bonding strength of the fufu dough, was determined to have an optimal threshold range of 0.36 – 0.51 (Figure 7), indicating the level at which the dough maintains its structural integrity while remaining palatable. The high coefficient of determination (88.35%) suggests a strong model fit to the data, reinforcing the reliability of this threshold. This trait is likely influenced by the interaction between cassava starch and water, as well as the processing conditions.

Figure 7: Threshold of Cohesiveness

2.2 THRESHOLD OF JAR AGAINST QDA

2.2.1 Threshold of Mouldability

The Figure 8 illustrates the relationship between Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) scores and Just-About-Right (JAR) ratings for mouldability, with an R^2 value of 0.805, indicating a strong correlation. For at least half of consumers to be satisfied, mouldability must exceed a QDA score of 5.95. This suggest that, if the intensity measured sensorially is less than 5.95, less than 50% of consumers are satisfied with mouldability. To meet the preference of at least 70% of consumers, the mouldability should be greater than 7.55. This indicates that consumers favor dough with a firmer and more cohesive structure, making it easier to shape and handle. The threshold range highlights the importance of achieving a balance in mouldability. If the dough is too soft (below 5.95), it may not hold its shape well, leading to a less desirable consumer experience. Therefore, optimizing cassava genotypes within the ideal range enhances consumer satisfaction and product acceptability.

Figure 8: Threshold of Mouldability

2.2.2 Threshold of Stickiness

Fufu stickiness is a measure of the dough tendency to adhere to the hand or fingers. Moderate level of fufu stickiness is required to produce a smooth, cohesive dough. . From the Figure 9, the optimal threshold of the stickiness ranges from 3.20 – 4.6. The coefficient of determination of 82.97% indicates a good fit of the model to our data..

Figure 9: Threshold of Stickiness

2.2.3 Threshold of Smoothness

Smoothness is a critical textural attribute that significantly influences the acceptability of fufu. The results presented in Figure 10 indicate that the optimal smoothness threshold for consumer preference falls within the range of 6.95 to 7.58, as highlighted by the orange-shaded region. This suggests that fufu dough exhibiting smoothness within this range is most desirable to consumers.

The quadratic trendline fitted to the data demonstrates a peak JAR score (~90%) around a smoothness value of 7.2–7.3, indicating the point of maximum consumer preference. Beyond this range, JAR scores decline, suggesting that either excessive or insufficient smoothness reduces consumer acceptability. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.891$) further supports the reliability of this relationship, indicating that smoothness strongly correlates with consumer preference.

Figure 10: Threshold of Smoothness

2.3 THRESHOLD OF JAR AGAINST COLOR (INSTRUMENT)

2.3.1 Threshold Analysis of Lightness (L_Colour) and consumer JAR

The study in Figure 11 examines the relationship between L_colour (brightness) values and Just-About-Right (JAR) scores to establish optimal and acceptable threshold values for consumer preference. A linear regression model was used to analyze the data, yielding an R^2 value of 0.7753, indicating a strong negative correlation between L_Colour and JAR scores. The optimal threshold of the L_colour corresponds to values below 58, and the acceptable threshold values below 65.6. Beyond this value, the likelihood of consumer rejection increases, meaning fufu with an L_colour higher than 61 is perceived as too light and less desirable.

Figure 11: Threshold Analysis of Lightness (L_Colour)

The graph Figure 12 illustrates the relationship between a^* _colour (on the x-axis) and consumer acceptability (JAR %) on the y-axis. The JAR score represents the percentage of consumers who find the fufu color "Just-About-Right." The trend in the graph indicates that as the a^* _colour value increases (becomes less negative, shifting towards a reddish hue), the percentage of consumers who find the color acceptable decreases. This strong correlation is evident from the regression analysis, which shows an R^2 value of 0.9347, confirming that color is a major factor influencing consumer preference.

One of the key findings from this analysis is the threshold of consumer acceptability at $JAR = 70\%$, which is a common benchmark for sensory evaluation in food science (Meilgaard et al., 2016). The red dashed line in the graph marks this threshold, indicating that at an a^* _colour value of approximately -6.0, at least **70% of consumers** still accept the fufu color as desirable. This suggests that fufu should maintain an a^* _colour of -6.0 or lower to ensure broad consumer acceptance.

As the a^* _colour moves closer to -5.0 or higher, the percentage of consumers who accept the color drops significantly. This is particularly evident when the JAR score falls below 50%, corresponding to an

a*_colour between -4.5 and -4.0. This suggests that when the fufu color shifts towards reddish or brownish tones, more than half of consumers find it unacceptable.

Figure 12: Threshold Analysis of a*_Colour impact

2.3.2 Threshold Analysis of b* Colour Impact with JAR fufu Product Acceptability

The Figure 13 shows the relationship between b*_color values and Just-About-Right (JAR) scores for cassava fufu color preference. The trend line suggests a negative correlation ($R^2 = 0.8934$), meaning that as b increases (more yellowish color), consumer acceptability (JAR) decreases. The b_value around 5 suggest high consumer acceptability (80–90% JAR). This indicates that fufu with a less yellowish color is generally preferred. The optimal threshold of the b*_colour value corresponding to the 70% JAR level was determined to be below 11.48, this implies that 70% of consumers accept fufu with b*_colour of below 11.48. Beyond this value, the likelihood of consumer rejection increases, meaning fufu with b*_colour higher than 25.02 is perceived as less desirable.

Figure 13: Threshold Analysis of b^* _Colour impact

The results of this study provide valuable insights for cassava breeding programs aimed at improving fufu quality. By selecting genotypes that meet or exceed the optimal thresholds for moldability, smoothness, stickiness, colour, hardness, adhesiveness, springiness, and cohesiveness, breeders can develop cassava varieties that produce superior fufu dough.

3 CONCLUSION

This comprehensive study successfully determined the threshold levels for key fufu dough attributes in seven contrasting cassava genotypes. The results indicate that these attribute—hardness, adhesiveness, springiness, and cohesiveness—can be reliably measured using instrumental analysis, with high precision accuracy. The findings provide a robust foundation for cassava breeding programs focused on improving fufu quality, as well as for cassava processors seeking to produce high-quality fufu products that meet consumer expectations.

Understanding the threshold levels for key fufu dough attributes allows for the development of products that align with consumer preferences. The identified optimal levels for moldability, smoothness, stickiness, colour, hardness, adhesiveness, springiness, and cohesiveness can serve as benchmarks for cassava processors and manufacturers, ensuring that their products meet market demands. Additionally, the findings highlight the importance of texture in consumer satisfaction, which can inform marketing strategies and product positioning.

REFERENCE

- Chijioke, U., Madu, T., Okoye, B., Ogunka, A. P., Ejechi, M., Ofoeze, M., Ogbete, C., Njoku, D., Ewuziem, J., Kalu, C., et al. (2021). Quality Attributes of Fufu in South-East Nigeria: A Guide for Cassava Breeders. *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.*, **56**(3), 1247–1257
- Bello, A., Olaosebikan, O., Oluwaseun O. A., Maziya-Dixon, B. and Teeken. B. (2020). Consumer Testing of Eba in Rural and Urban Areas in Nigeria. Understanding the Drivers of Trait Preferences and the Development of Multi-User RTB Product Profiles, WP1. RTBfoodsProjectCIRAD, Ibadan, p. 26 (2020).
- Ndjouenkeu. R., NgoualemKegah, F., Teeken, B., Okoye, B., Madu, T., Olaosebikan, O.D. et al., (2021). From cassava to gari: mapping of quality characteristics and end-user preferences in Cameroon and Nigeria. *Int J FoodSciTechnol.*, **56**:1223–1238.
- Obilie, E.M., Tano-Debrah, K. and Amoa-Awua, W.K. (2004). Souring and breakdown of cyanogenic glucosides during the processing of cassava into akyeke. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 93:115–121.
- Olaosebikan, O., Abolore, B., Teeken, B. and Forsythe, L. (2022) Gendered Food Mapping on Gari/Eba in Nigeria. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/7056977> [cited 2023 Jan 24].
- RTBfoods Laboratory Standard Operating Procedure, <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00595>
- Teeken, B, Agbona, A., Bello, A., Olaosebikan, O., Alamu, E., Adesokan, M. et al., (2021) Understanding cassava varietal preferences through pairwise ranking of gari-eba and fufu prepared by local farmer-processors. *Int J Food Sci. Technol.* **56**:1258–1277.
- Teeken, B., Bello, A., Olaosebikan, O. and Edughaen, G. (2022). TRICOT method applied to consumer testing for the selection of high quality RTB hybrids, from end-user perspective. RTB foods project webinar